

Society and its specific laws of development

1. **Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich.** Professor of Tashkent State Transport University.
2. **Xudoyberdiev Dyorbek Shokirovich.** Student of Tashkent State Transport University.

Abstract

In the article, nature, things and events in it, the laws of their development, and society, the essence of events and their laws of development are completely different from each other, because the creation, development and future fate of society, its laws of development, and the future fate of all humanity, or rather, its activity dependence was analyzed.

Key words: development, progress, legality, state, society, change.

INTRODUCTION

Perfection and effective functioning of the management system, which plays an important role in regulating social relations, depends on both the managers and the managed. But experience shows that the relationship between them was not always smooth. In a way, this is natural. Because the managers and the managed

are based on the principle of dialectics with some aspects¹. That is, they are opposite to each other, and at the same time, one cannot exist without the other. Sometimes one side, sometimes the other side shows the "initiative" for the origin of the conflict between them. On the one hand, there are immoral vices such as injustice, impudence, arrogance, selfishness, arrogance, committed by managers, on the other hand, harmful habits such as irresponsibility, ingratitude, indiscipline, not realizing and not fulfilling one's duties, committed by the community, on the other hand, are the reasons for such "initiative" to be shown. will be By the way, if we think about duties.

MAIN PART

In this regard, we considered it permissible to cite the following comments of Hegel, who founded the theory of dialectical laws and categories and conducted significant research in other areas of philosophy:

"Man's duties are divided into four:

- 1) to his duties;
- 2) to those in front of the family;
- 3) to those before the state;
- 4) to those in front of other people.

Duty is important in regulating the relations between the state and the citizens, not only between the rulers and the ruled, but also in society as a whole. In legal terms, duty is the fulfillment of the obligations of citizens set by the state and society. True, the state, along with imposing duties on its citizens, also gave them

¹ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

certain rights and freedoms. The stable and effective functioning of the system of social relations mainly depends on citizens' equal observance of their duties and rights and freedoms. But there is an unpleasant situation that is often observed. Citizens know their rights and freedoms very well, even more than usual. At the same time, they freeze the demand for their rights and freedoms. Unfortunately, we do not always observe such attitudes of citizens towards their duties. Usually some citizens don't know or don't want to know their duties². Билган тақдирларида эса унга панжа орасидан қарайдилар ва уни бажаришни пайсалга солиб юрадилар. Аммо, фуқаролар бир нарсани унутмасликлари лозимки, жамиятда ўрнатилган бурчлар бажариш мажбурийдир. Хусусан, Ўзбекистон Республикасида ҳам, “Барча фуқаролар Конституцияда белгилаб қўйилган бурчларни бажарадилар”³. If the citizens do not fulfill their obligations voluntarily, the state will force them to do so. The state has sufficient means of coercion and structures for the use of force. But this is an unpleasant situation, harmful to the nature of civil society. Because one of the important principles of the civil society is determined by the fact that the citizens fully understand the meaning of their duties, rights and freedoms established in the society, and most importantly, they consciously follow them.

There is something - a phenomenon in the world that is doomed to change. Only some of these changes happen in very short moments before our eyes, while other changes take days, months, and years to manifest themselves. For some

² Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

³ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси. 11 – боб, 47 – модда.

changes to take place, human life may be lacking. Examples include the movement of subterranean plates, the formation of mountains, and volcanoes. Many philosophers who left a mark in the history of philosophy have views on this topic. In particular, Hegel, who brought the science of philosophy to a completely new level, "understanding progress on the basis of dialectics shows that the phenomena of nature and society are diverse and its transition from one state to another, as well as the right way to know the laws of development of nature and society." In this place, the phenomena of nature and society and the laws of development of nature and society are combined and expressed as a whole. The goal is clear - to explain the essence of things and events in a general, holistic way. However, we must not forget one thing that nature, things and events in it, the laws of their development, and society, the events in it and the laws of their development, are completely different from each other⁴. You and I have read a lot about these differences in philosophy and other scientific and artistic books. Let's dwell on them in the same way. We know that nature is said to have come into existence before man, independent of human consciousness and thought. We agree with this one hundred percent. Then again it is said that nature develops according to its own laws, which cannot be changed. 100 years ago, one could agree 100 percent with this opinion, but now objectionable aspects have appeared. Even now, we cannot influence some laws of nature. For example, the rotation of the earth around the sun and its rotation around its axis and hokoza. However, with the growth of human intelligence and the development of science and technology, sometimes

⁴ Салимов Б. Л., Мазбутов Д., Жўраев А. (2022). ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ТЕНГЛИК ВА ТЕНГСИЗЛИК ҚОНУНЛАР ВА УРФ -ОДАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО БОҒЛИҚЛИГИ. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(6), 11–17.

knowingly, sometimes unknowingly, it began to influence nature and its development laws. Unfortunately, in many cases this effect is negative. For example, heat and toxic gases emitted from internal combustion engines, heating furnaces, factories and other industrial facilities rise into the atmosphere and cause global climate changes on earth. As a result, disproportionate and incomprehensible situations occur in the laws of the change of seasons. Among these are low snowfalls, warm days in the cold of winter, and warmer than normal days. I mean, man did not create the laws of nature, its development, but man affects some of the laws of nature with his activities. However, this effect is mostly negative.

The emergence, development, and future fate of society, its laws of development, depends on the whole of humanity, or rather, on its activities⁵. Hegel said, "Man is so versatile that anything can be made of him..."⁶. Since society is made up of people, we will try to apply this idea to the concept of society. Then the following reasoning arises: society is such a comprehensive, multifaceted thing that it can be developed in various ways and forms. In fact, it was so. If we flip through the history books, we will be convinced of this. Until today, how many countries have lived, that is, how many societies have existed. Even now, there are more than 230 countries in the world, and there are as many different societies. Be it the societies of the past or the societies of the present, none of them are alike.

⁵ Салимов Б. Л., Мазбутов Д., Жўраев А. (2022). ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ТЕНГЛИК ВА ТЕНГСИЗЛИК ҚОНУНЛАР ВА УРФ -ОДАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО БОҒЛИҚЛИГИ. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(6), 11–17.

⁶ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

Everything is different. This is also a proof of our conclusion stated above.

It should be noted about the society that the conditions of its existence and the laws of development are constantly developing and changing. No matter how favorable the conditions in any flourishing society, no matter how well-developed its development path and laws of development are, all these are of relative importance. These areas require constant updating and improvement. Otherwise, they will become uncomfortable and outdated over time.

It is known that in every period, in every region, every nation and people adapts its society to itself and builds it the way it wants. In this process, the influence of national leaders, political figures, religious leaders and representatives of science was strong. In today's democratic, civil society, all citizens are involved in this process⁷.

Because it has already been proven that the society will be effective if it is built based on the interests of all the citizens living here, and not on the basis of specific categories.

CONCLUSION

However, the process of reaching such a correct conclusion was not easy. For centuries, societies have lived on completely wrong principles. Even mature thinkers of his time like Hegel sometimes advocated such unnecessary ideas. In particular, Hegel "advocates the class system of society, and expresses his opposition to the presence of representatives of the people in the management of the state. He advocates a special role of the noble class in society, and even

⁷ Салимов Б. Л., Мазбутов Д., Жўраев А. (2022). ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ТЕНГЛИК ВА ТЕНГСИЗЛИК ҚОНУНЛАР ВА УРФ -ОДАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО БОҒЛИҚЛИГИ. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(6), 11–17.

justifies the privilege of the nobles in the administration of the state. We must admit and mention that Hegel's contribution to the development of the science of philosophy is great. The development of philosophical laws and categories by him served to increase the level of philosophical thinking. Also, Hegel's scientific works in the history of philosophy and other areas of philosophy have a fair share for the development of science. No one wants to deny this. However, one cannot agree with some of Hegel's views on the state and society. In particular, one cannot agree with the conclusions that promote great statism, nationalism and racism. Because such ideas eventually lead to conflicts between nations and peoples, disagreements between states.

REFERENCES

1. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Конституцияси. 11 – боб, 47 – модда.
2. Ziyodulla Davronov. Falsafa. Toshkent. Iqtisod-moliya. 2006. 269 бет.
3. Сержило тафаккур дурдоналаридан. Тошкент. “Navro’z”. 2003. 297 бет.
4. С.Йулдошев, М.Усмонов, Р. Каримов, Г.Қобулниёзова, Г.Рузматова. Янги ва энг янги давр Ғарбий Европа фалсафаси (XV II—XX асрлар). Т.: “Шарк”. 2002. 144 бет.
5. Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.
6. Салимов Б. Л., Мазбутов Д., Жўраев А. (2022). ИЖТИМОЙ МУНОСАБАТЛАРДА ТЕНГЛИК ВА ТЕНГСИЗЛИК ҚОНУНЛАР ВА

УРФ -ОДАТЛАРНИНГ ЎЗАРО БОҒЛИҚЛИГИ. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(6), 11–17.